

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies: Methodology and Guidelines

- Preliminary TAIS, September 2020-

Deliverable D3.3

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Del. 3.3 TAIS methodology and guidelines. Preliminary version [September, 2020]

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About RAISD	
Call (part) identifier	H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018
Topic	MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement
Fixed EC Keywords	Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author.

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RAISD Glossary

ARU	Action Research Unit
EC	European Commission
FDP	Forcibly Displaced People / Person
HVG	Highly Vulnerable Group
LGTBIQ	Lesbian, Gay, Transgender, Bisexual, Intersex and Queer or Questioning
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PRSF	Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum
RAISD	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
RCT	Randomized Controlled Trial
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
RSS	Refugee Support System
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Time-based
TAIS	Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
VC	Vulnerability Context
VG	Vulnerable Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The main working hypothesis in the RAISD project is that effective and appropriate strategies of attention and inclusion for highly vulnerable groups of forcibly displaced people need to be tailored to their specific vulnerability context.

TAIS is the acronym for "Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies". It means implementing personalised attention and inclusion activities that are designed to respond to the specific needs of a particular vulnerable group.

According to the methodology, each of the seven Action Research Units of the project selected a vulnerability context that could be the beneficiary, and designed its specific TAIS for it. Then, the project implements the TAIS in collaboration with the network of their Action Research Units.

RAISD consortium members started the TAIS design process in the first quarter of 2020 and by July 2020, all the countries had a clear implementation plan, and some of the partners had even started with the first steps of their application. The main TAIS activities are planned to take place in Phase 1 (in Autumn 2020), and Phases 2 and 3 (from December 2020 to September 2021), with a partial evaluation between phases that considers all the available information until that moment. Phase 4 is entirely dedicated to the cross-country evaluation of the TAIS final results in the 7 project countries. Along this process, the consortium will continuously monitor what adjustments and adaptations will be required to adapt the TAIS to the changing conditions of today's liquid world, and especially to the modifications in local migration policies and living conditions of forcibly displaced people. The key feature for adapting our TAIS to the forthcoming conditions are having resilience, anticipating difficulties, and, above all, listening to our beneficiaries and other stakeholders.

The TAIS are designed and put in practice in Spain, Italy, Hungary, Finland, Turkey, Lebanon, and Jordan.

The TAIS in Spain is aimed at promoting the socioeconomic inclusion of Sub-Saharan women, refugees or asylum-seekers. In collaboration with diverse stakeholders, the objective is to develop a process of training and support in entrepreneurship. The final objective is that target participants acquire the knowledge and skills to create a cooperative or other kind of association that support their economic autonomy.

In Italy, the TAIS seeks for Change Management in Education Delivery Approaches fostering a bottom-up and participatory practice to education, shifting from an INDUCED training offer approach (dominating and top-down way to organize education for forced displaced people) to a SELECTIVE approach in developing a training experience in which several optional learning outcomes are offered and participants can choose contents that are attractive for them.

In Hungary, the objective of the TAIS is to enhance refugees' embedding in social structures. Social workers and service providers analyse individual cases in order to build a "Trajectory monitoring toolbox" of helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. It contains evidence-based "vulnerability profiles" as well as the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow in the institutional field, in order to prevent the accumulation of vulnerabilities and to reduce the isolation of vulnerable individuals.

In Finland, two TAIS have been implemented:

TAIS I: To reduce the level of confinement of young men within the Finnish reception system and to promote their non-formal learning, a multilingual online forum is established. Both asylum seeking men and Finnish-speaking voluntary men are invited to join the forum. The aim is to discuss everyday life and study and work opportunities in Finland while fostering asylum seekers' language proficiencies.

TAIS2: To promote the wellbeing of asylum-seeking families with small children, day-care activities within the Finnish reception system will be developed. The current state in which the access to child-care services is restricted, the children's integration and mental wellbeing and parents' ability to use the services they are entitled to are severely hampered. Two reception centres providing child-care services and interested in developing them further will be involved to benchmark the model of child-care services in reception centres.

In Turkey, the TAIS main beneficiary target group are Syrian women. The TAIS aims to ensure that vulnerable groups' access and participation in basic daily life practices can be systematically followed through monitoring, with the participation of vulnerable groups and host community members. Although there are activities that ensure the realization of basic daily life practices of forcibly displaced people, these activities are sometimes insufficient. In addition, forcibly displaced people cannot access and are unaware of the activities that exist due to various reasons (language barriers, cultural differences, prejudices in the host society, etc.). Through monitoring, it will be possible to determine in which areas additional activities and support are required.

In Lebanon, the designed TAIS geared at addressing social, emotional, and academic problems. The program will have a positive impact on the Syrian people in camps in addition to delivering a holistic Corona Virus awareness to children, pregnant women, elderly people, malnourished people, and people who are ill or immune-compromised. RAISD team in Lebanon, through its Health committee will work to enrich all stakeholders with the coping tools needed to enhance them in developing their awareness and minimize the challenges in facing the COVID 19 pandemic trauma.

Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF) in Jordan aims to provide a structure that significantly contributes to the well-being of individuals and prevents the need for medical support through non-clinical interventions. It also aims to promote awareness and understanding of the importance of Psychosocial Support System (PSS). Five different topics will be implemented by the PRSF: economic empowerment and promoting financial knowledge, social support and refugee status, health and legal awareness, and fostering psychological well-being. Moreover, RAISD-YU team attempts to create the Refugee Support System portal "RSS", which was established to spread awareness of the benefits of PSS, provide PSS to refugees, and collect and preserve data.

The project team and the actors started by gathering information and demonstrating an implementable approach to TAISs. Thereafter, they addressed the deeper understanding of the contextual factors influencing outcomes, as well as the logics of the actors' involvement.

Each ARU is working collaboratively with **as diverse stakeholders as possible**, in order to comply with some of the activities of an RRI architecture process [Deblonde, 2015].

With this knowledge, a methodology for the analysis of VCs and the development of TAISs was designed and applied. In this way, the **information** used in the project comes mainly **from the own actors**. Literature in the domain plays a secondary role. With this approach, real data from actual situations has guided the definition of contexts and related elements, instead of superimposing a priori categories.

1.5 How are the TAIS evaluated?

Before designing the TAIS, the following **criteria** were considered:

- Specific: what the TAIS plans to achieve must be very clear.
- Measurable: its development must be properly defined and measured through indicators.
- Achievable: the objectives must be established proportionally at micro and meso levels (contributions of time and money must provide sufficient results)
- Relevant: the TAIS must be related to the vulnerability and the existing needs based on the interviews and previous work of the ARU.
- Based on time: a complete project cycle must be planned, and the time frame must be realistic / feasible.
- Sustainable: indicators that enable their duration in the medium and long term must be identified.

TAIS evaluation is based on an **actor-oriented definition of indicators**.

The indicators for the TAIS are discussed in terms of the following categories:

- a) Hierarchy: input/output – outcome/result – impact.
It is suggested that lower level indicators should be set (input/output).
- b) Perspective: process-oriented – result-oriented.
It is suggested that result-oriented indicators should be given priority.
- c) Evaluation: baseline, interim, final.
It is suggested that baseline and final are a must, interim indicators only if reasonable.

The exact evaluation criteria should be set up individually for each TAIS by its participants, in line with RAISD's Work Package 7. The [evaluation criteria were fully detailed in previous Del. 7.3](#).

RAISD pilots will be implemented in three iterative cycles. Throughout the cycles, the focus is on increasing the pilot's feasibility for users. There are three general evaluation criteria:

Table 1. General evaluation criteria

General criteria	Tasks	Methods	Timing
Defining needs	Conceptualising vulnerabilities and vulnerability contexts	Literature, statistics and stakeholder and FDP interviews	Before starting the pilots
Defining mechanisms	Determining what happens during the pilots and how they are implemented and perceived	Qualitative interviews, participatory observation, action research	During the first two pilot cycles
Defining outcomes	Determining the level of change the piloted activities provoke and estimating their costs	Quantitative datasets, follow-up surveys, register data, data from online sources	Before and after the last pilot cycle

2 What methodology principles are used for designing TAIS?

The project adopts a research strategy based on **methodological triangulation**. It comprehends **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)**, **action research**, and **socio-ecological models**. Besides, as a both theoretical and technical tool, **gender mainstreaming** is applied.

2.1 RRI and gender perspective

At the overall level, RAISD adopts an RRI approach [Owen et al., 2012]. RRI focuses on the need of co-creating research activities where all the relevant stakeholders play an active role in its definition, execution and evaluation.

Research needs must arise, first of all, from the social group. This is the 1st phase, where the rest of the stakeholders work to contribute ideas from their diverse perspectives. Due to that, the TAIS design is not started until the group for which the action research is being carried out is consulted. Therefore, the first step would be to select the vulnerable group of our TAIS.

The ARUs should have a representative from each helix to design the TAIS. It is necessary to promote a balance in terms of public / private sector, for-profit / non-profit sector, ethnicity, gender and local communities. As well as ensuring that ethical issues are respected throughout the project: gender equality, informed consent, accessibility, respect for diversity, etc.

2.2 Action Research

The actual work in the units that conform the project follow an Action Research approach [Stringer, 2013]. Such approach advocates the use of context dependent procedures that are developed through inquiry in the specific setting, instead of the application of general standardised practices. The project implements a specific participatory action research approach to study the VGs.

The anticipation and reflection of action research enable to visualise the impact on society and reflect the underlying values and objectives of research in the short, medium, and long term.

This methodology guarantees that the project is flexible and that it can be adapted to the changes in the needs of the action research expressed by participants. This methodology is inclusive since it incorporates the opinions of the stakeholders and of the social group that participates in the TAIS throughout all the process. It implies making the project accessible to all stakeholders (including the social group of beneficiaries) in all its phases.

2.3 Socio ecological models

These models are intended to analyse a social setting in a holistic way, at different levels of abstraction and from different perspectives. Levels of intervention:

- a) Micro level: individual / interpersonal. Family and affective-emotional context.
- b) Meso level: institutional. Interactions with communities of origin, receiving communities during transit and at destination, contexts of groups and associations, etc.
- c) Macro level: policy / law. It is very unlikely that we can achieve results at the macro level during the project.

Macro level vs. meso / micro level: the macro level is the context to consider all the time. Recommendations directed at the macro level can be written, but TAIS must be implemented at the meso / micro level. If an obstacle is found at the macro level, which makes a given TAIS proposal unfeasible, it must be modified to be feasible.

3 How are the TAIS designed in the seven participating countries?

3.1 Spain

3.1.1 Basic information:

The TAIS in Spain is aimed at promoting the socioeconomic inclusion of Sub-Saharan women, refugees or asylum-seekers (applicants for international protection whose application has been accepted, rejected or is pending resolution). In collaboration with different stakeholders, the objective is to develop a process of training and support in entrepreneurship. The final objective is that target participants acquire the knowledge and skills to create a cooperative or other kind of association that support their economic autonomy, and, possibly, that they make the first actions in the entrepreneurship direction. It has a strong perspective on social participation. Women are protagonists: key actors at the centre of the action.

Table 2. TAIS resume in Spain

UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain		
Beneficiary collective	Sub-Saharan women TRAINING COURSE IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP	
Place	Online process; Cross national	
Phase	Main activities of each cycle	Dates
1	Promotion of group cohesion, (identification of common interests, work on the identification of strengths and individual contributions to the group, identification of possible productive themes) & improvement of personal and social competencies for entrepreneurship and employment	June - Nov. 2020
2	Professional development and leadership at work Active entrepreneurship and management	Dec. 2020 – April 2021
3	Active entrepreneurship and management Personalized support for financing and start-up	May - Sept. 2021
	Final cross analysis	Oct. 2021 - Jan. 2022

3.1.2 How was the design process and who participated in it?

TAIS in Spain was designed inside the ARU's processes, according to the RAISD design guidelines. UCM coordinated the progressions. The first phase comprised the analysis and recommendations obtained in the interviews of FDP and previous ARU's focus groups and meetings (2019). After sharing the diagnosis of the most highly vulnerable groups in Spain, the **5th UCM ARU meeting** (February 25th) identified two potential proposals of TAIS. Afterwards, one TAIS was selected once viability, relevance and sustainability in the medium and long term

were studied. Both were considered from the perspective of being measurable, specific, and achievable according to the timeline established in the project.

The second phase focused on the identification of activities to meet the inclusion needs of the identified profile (Sub-Saharan women seeking international protection). Therefore, on the **6th UCM ARU meeting** (held online 12th May). The attendees were divided into smaller groups to develop a TAIS-design. All focus groups agreed on the need for economic inclusion and *entrepreneurship, as well as* on the idea of an association of women that could lead to a workers' cooperative. In parallel, the team consulted some representatives of the target collectives to have a first approach to their needs and assessment of the situation. The conclusions of these meetings were aligned with those of the ARU members.

The third phase focused on the contrast, feedback and participation of potential beneficiaries. Thus, after locating a wider group of this profile, and in order to guarantee women's participation, an **online meeting** was held with 12 potential beneficiaries of our TAIS (16th June). It was organised through three focus groups with WhatsApp video calls. The team evaluated with the participants the objectives, interests, needs and means. Afterwards, the **7th UCM ARU meeting** was held (online 22nd June). A summary of the conclusions of the meeting with potential beneficiaries was shared. The attendees of the ARU meeting were divided into smaller working-groups to develop the final design of the TAIS: its basic content and approaches of social intervention. These results were also shared and discussed **individually with the final beneficiaries** from 29th to 30th June. Thus, the design was fully validated.

The fourth phase includes the programming and scheduling of activities, the accompaniment of the beneficiaries for their participation, and the location of resources for the implementation of the TAIS. After the participatory process, the content of the training for the cooperative has been shared with UCM ARU members to identify the resources of each organisation, UCM included. The TAIS was also shared and commented **with other organisations** that work with Sub-Saharan women seeking international protection.

The members of the ARU that were more active during the design were ACCEM, CEAR, La Merced, Cáritas, La Rueca, Mundo en Movimiento, Ashoka, Red Cross, Asociación Empleo y Desarrollo, UNHCR, Madrid and Alcobendas Councils and one researcher (Mohammed Dahiri); as well as final beneficiaries and UCM RAISD team and its collaborators. Nantik Lum is playing a key role since June in the entrepreneurship area.

The fifth phase is the beginning of the TAIS in July, with a 4-week training module on the RAISD project and female entrepreneurship.

3.1.3 *How did you consider and incorporate the methodology principles into the TAIS design?*

3.1.3.1 **RRI Responsible Research and Innovation**

The needs addressed by the TAIS arose from the interviews to FDP and ARU meetings: Sub-Saharan women was the social group that stood out as especially vulnerable among the FDP. Lack of stable work was the most reported problem by all FDP profiles. As we have previously detailed in question 1.1.2, the final TAIS design was developed in three ARU meetings, with the validation of two phases of consultation with final beneficiaries. Besides, our ARU is growing with the participation of **other organisations** that work with Sub-Saharan women seeking international

protection. Many of them were unable to attend the last ARU meeting because of their agendas and the current social situation, but they were able to contribute by means of individual online meetings.

This process offers an innovative approach to address the needs of attention and inclusion in FD, putting at the core of the design the beneficiaries and their host communities. It also presents important challenges, as it demands a continuous adaptation of the TAIS structure to findings and needs, and changing the classical roles of all the collectives, including target groups and researchers.

All RRI helixes are represented in UCM ARU. However, most of its entities are NGOs. The helix that is more underrepresented is business organisations. Two organizations that are specialized in social entrepreneurship (Ashoka and Nantik Lum) are part of the ARU. As the team is contacting more organisations specialised in entrepreneurship and with specific examples of entrepreneurship, it is expected that the representatives for the helix of business and industry will increase in UCM ARU.

Regarding gender equity, more than the 65% of attendees to 5th, 6th and 7th ARU meetings were women. Beneficiaries of the TAIS are women. In the research team, there are gender female experts who review and implement this perspective in all the aspects of the research processes.

The process was open and transparent. The final decisions were made according to previously established criteria (viability, relevance and sustainability in the medium and long term; considering if the potential results were measurable, specific, and achievable in time) and the limitations of the COVID situation.

All RAISD ethical requirements have been met. We have obtained the oral informed consent of all participants in the TAIS. Other oral consents have been gathered because of COVID situation, such as rights of image in ARU online meetings attendees.

3.1.3.2 Action research

Beneficiaries' needs and interests are at the centre of the design. First, by prioritising diagnosis results, and contrasting them with the key collective through online groups and individual interviews. Secondly, by opening outcomes and design possibilities to NGOs which co-designed the TAIS, and which results were again open to the participants. Besides, TAIS design has taken into account several mechanisms to foster action research, in particular regarding the adaptation to actual findings: individualized follow-up of participants, contrast and monitoring from ARUS, sessions open to the spontaneous demands and needs of the participants, and the formal evaluation cycles, with specific spaces for evaluating the processes and results by participants, the ARU and external collaborators.

In this context, there are demands of experts to address specific aspects of entrepreneurship. These experts have been invited to participate both in the ARU and the TAIS process. In fact, all the research is continuously open to society (and in particular to experts in some required field), who can join the groups to help to fulfil the TAIS needs and to improve the overall quality of the process. This also contributes to create feedback loops between those involved in the project and the external community, being able to react to those situations emerging at every phase.

3.1.3.3 Socio ecological models

The Spanish TAIS strategy takes place and affect above all micro (interpersonal/individual) levels, as well as meso (institutional) levels.

Concerning the micro level and the TAIS design, the individual/familiar conditions of the beneficiaries are being considered, for instance for the timetable of activities and presential/online activities. The team has continuous conversations with the FDP to identify difficulties due to family responsibilities, administrative process, or accessibility issues, and adapt the TAIS to these.

Meso level is considered specifically as TAIS has been co-designed with public and public-funding organizations, as well as private NGOs, that are responsible for official measures and programs for the inclusion of refugees and asylum-seekers in Spain. Impacts at the institutional level are expected in terms of gender issues and the inclusion of the entrepreneurship perspective within the economic itineraries of inclusion of the highly VG. Some of our findings are already having impact in the institutions. For instance, the team noticed in the work with FDP in the TAIS that they do not have enough training in language and labour orientation, and organizations do not provide enough resources for that. Policy makers acknowledged in our ARU meetings that situation and some of them have committed to review their policies related to trainings.

Macro policies are not contemplated at this moment, although our outcomes and policy recommendations will help the cross-national analysis regarding recommendation for inclusion policies. In our case, policies regarding the attention and inclusion strategies for refugees and asylum-seekers in the line of tailoring them to the features of specific groups and host communities. The TAIS will also have an indirect influence in policymaking once the research and the TAIS intervention have concluded, as they can offer a demonstration effect and inspire new regulations.

3.1.4 Beneficiary collective/s, their needs and how these were detected, the host communities

TAIS was designed precisely for the target collective after an exhaustive fieldwork research and with ARU activities contributing decisively. The decisions were based on FDP and expert interviews, which allow discovering the collective's needs. As explained in 1.12, participants are currently actively participating in the design and readjustments/tailoring of the TAIS.

The previous mechanisms have also been used to work on the engagement and benefits for the host communities. One objective of TAISs is to promote and create welcoming communities: to establish ties between the collective and the host community. With our TAIS, host communities will benefit from a richer entrepreneur context, a better integrated community, and also a less vulnerable community which makes more visible its active contribution to the host society. Nevertheless, the team considers that there is still much work to do with the host community. It is currently looking for new opportunities for the target collective in the host context. For instance, it is working together with organizations specialized in entrepreneurship and economic development, which are usually not linked to the reality of refuge and international protection. These organisations have here the opportunity to learn about refugees and become involved with the well-being of this group. In addition, they can see first-hand their full potential and the contributions they can make to the economic growth of the societies that are hosting them.

Regarding the actors' participation, the team highlights that the 5th UCM ARU meeting was held with 3 asylum seekers, representatives of non-profit entities (ACCEM, Tayba Association of Young Muslims, Caritas, La Merced, Mundo en Movimiento and Red Cross), 2 researchers, a representative of the policy maker helix (Spanish Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration), a representative of a non-profit organization specialized in social entrepreneurship (Ashoka), and a representative of a non-profit entity with some functions in the administration system (La Rueca). The main objective of this workshop was to start the design of 3 TAIS proposals with three VGs among the FDP. With this aim, 3 focus groups were created. Before the focus group activities of the TAIS, a summary of the recommendations obtained in the interviews of FDP were shared with the ARU.

Two of the three proposals were focused on the same VG (i.e. female asylum seekers of sub-Saharan origin), and the other on transgender women asylum seekers. The final decision of the target group derived from the ARU, experts, and FDP that were interviewed during the fieldwork. Collective needs were explored by means of interviews, ARU meetings with experts and FDP, online meetings and phone calls with final beneficiaries and literature review.

As already explained, the final beneficiaries have a key role in the readjustments/tailoring of the TAIS. They participated in two consultation processes during the design, and they will be able to adjust the contents that they consider necessary for the development of the TAIS and the design of the cooperative. Furthermore, their opinion will be essential during the evaluation periods of the TAIS. The final beneficiaries have been asked to participate in the ARU meetings and the team hopes that some interested women can be incorporated little by little.

3.1.5 Collaborating actors

The implementation, development and evaluation of TAIS will be coordinated by project researchers. Some advisory board members support and take part as collaborators of the TAIS (facilitators) (e.g. Elena Vázquez, ACCEM). The key participants in the process include collaborators and ARU Members (e.g. Ashoka, Asociación Madrid Empleo y Desarrollo (AMED), Ayuntamiento De Alcobendas, Ayuntamiento de Madrid, CEAR, CONSENS, Fundación La Merced Migraciones, Fundación Recover Hospitales para África, Kifkif, La Rueca, Proyecto Esperanza-Adoratrices, Red Acoge, and San Ricardo Pampuri). Besides, new stakeholders have been involved as collaborating actors: Fundación Nantik Lum and Speak Madrid.

Currently UCM is working to implicate external promoters/sponsors related to the helix of business and firms. This is an ongoing process all through the TAIS. Some of them are Cooperama and REAS Mercado Social.

3.1.6 Adaptation to Covid 19

There have been adjustments to the TAIS activities so far due to Covid19 measures. Other foreseen risks for the TAIS are also considered, such as the dropout rate of the participants, which is usually higher in online teaching. Despite of it, there are not more foreseen risks to the TAIS and its design.

In the case of UCM ARU, headquartered in Madrid (Spain), the team experienced an absolute impossibility to work with the target groups and to hold face-to-face meetings during the first months of the pandemic. The TAIS was refurbished to be developed in an online environment, at least during the first and the second round of pilots.

Although there were fewer restrictions in July, it was agreed to keep the online format for the safety of the participants. All beneficiaries have received a tablet with Internet connection at their homes to be able to follow the TAIS. Women have also received training in the use of these electronic devices.

All meetings and consultations are currently remote. This is also applied to ARU meetings, UCM RAISD team meetings, specific meetings with ARU members and all meetings with final beneficiaries.

During the first months of the COVID crisis, the emergency work of the entities of the ARU and the lack of technological resources and computer skills of vulnerable groups (that has been confirmed by UCM ARU entities) seriously delayed the design and implementation of the TAIS.

The current situation in Madrid, with a second wave of the pandemic, keeps the necessity of having TAIS activities online. Nevertheless, the team considers that some face-to-face activities are desirable to boost and improve the dynamics in the groups and the training process. Therefore, it is looking for possibilities to hold safely these eventual meetings at the university.

The FDP will participate in the design by default as it's them having direct influence over their own learning path's contents and modalities according to a set of individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, language knowledge, logistics and time availability, etc.).

3.2.3 How did you consider and incorporate the methodology principles into the TAIS design?

3.2.3.1 RRI Responsible Research and Innovation

The need for the TAIS arises from the research findings including HVG interviews, stakeholder fieldwork and the national and regional context analysis. In fact, the TAIS satisfies most of the identified 74 actor-oriented criteria [75% 'Yes' + 21% 'Partially' + 4% 'No'] adopted to evaluate policies and practices of attention towards Vulnerable Groups among FDP (as identified under 5.1).

The design process had started right when the C-19 lockdown come into force; therefore, it was unfeasible to gather with FDP representatives, although indirect consulting cooperation with the HVG women shelters continued. Due to the urgent need for HVG basic service provisions, there was a limitation in asking contribution and feedback on their behalf.

The quintuple helix was represented at different levels within the different design working groups, contributing to identify initial TAIS ideas that apply as many actor-oriented criteria as possible. Design adjustments followed ARU's members' feedback in terms of essential elements to be included in the final TAIS piloting (e.g. need for prior Italian language proficiency assessment; duration of participants' orientation period; importance of mentors with migratory background; to offer baby parking service; to produce user-friendly hard copy aids for participants, such as printed brochures and Trainees' Diary to record and evaluate their selective learning path as it develops).

The action-research findings highlighted women's inequity conditions in terms of rights, benefits and opportunities. Therefore, the TAIS aims at increasing HV female participation in education and training programs, decreasing their initial resistance and attendance reluctance and decreasing the dropout rates by avoiding the excessive strictness of traditional learning paths and hours of commitment and replacing these by a flexible learning environment.

Founding elements of the Transparent Research approach have been taken into consideration particularly during fieldwork activities, which findings (data collection, analysis, and report writing) have led to the identification of TAIS main target beneficiaries and to highlight peculiar needs to be addressed by a novelty strategy to implement.

Due to ethical issues the openness of data has been partially restricted to not compromise anonymity of research participants, producing only qualitative analyses and making aggregate level data available to the ARU members and the wider working groups through¹. Open access will further be improved so that data can potentially be reanalysed and synthesized by academics in future studies and by practitioners and managers for interventions planning.

The TAIS actors promote an inclusion practice designed to meet the needs of a diverse vulnerable learners' population adopting an identity, culture and gender-oriented approach along the whole process. Actors promote

¹ <https://cesie.org/en/higher-education-and-research/competence-cell-achievements-2019/>

the respect and the valorisation of the cultural, linguistic and historical characteristics of the participants, as well as, enhancing migrants' knowledge of those of the local population.

The TAIS Training Course (TC) participants will be requested to sign a "Learners' Agreement", stating to actively commit to attend all 90 hours of the Training Course in order to achieve the objectives promoted by the learning path. Moreover, they will be asked to sign "Release of use of likeness" document - to obtain and use as the Released Party sees fit the voice, image, photograph, likeness, video, and/or any other form of media as it develops (henceforth collectively referred to as Likeness). CESIE meanwhile undertakes not to use such images and likenesses in manners that might be offensive to the dignity and reputation of the undersigned.

3.2.3.2 Action research

Meeting individual needs is at core of the TAIS Strategy that adopts the novelty *Selective Approach*. To date, in most national and European Learning and Training Environments, it is common practices that target groups are pushed into a programme flow and imposed content as considered relevant and exploitable by the training providers and content designing stakeholders. This new Strategy allows HVG to be the directors of the learning content according to their own interest and needs, as they will be able to select among different areas/fields of knowledge.

The TAIS design is flexible in the training content and delivery modes so as to meet as much as possible the needs of different ranges of educational attainments (from the highly educated to those with only a basic level of education, or limited to informal and non-formal), Italian languages proficiency and time availability.

The three TAIS TC phases as to be experienced by the participants (i. orientation, ii training and study visits, iii evaluation and data analysis) will serve to adjust flexibility issues to better respond to their micro-level needs and real-life conditions. Ultimately, the recommendations will enhance collective reflections about the needed changes within the traditional Education Delivery Approaches at a macro-level.

Participation of quintuple helix representatives will be boosted by each one of them hosting (out of 5) planned participants' Study Visits, as integral part of the *ALL you can LEARN* training course. It will be an occasion for open discussion and consultation for both sides.

3.2.3.3 Socio ecological models

To respond to micro-level individual/familiar conditions and needs, the TAIS training will be offered in morning and afternoon sessions (participants chose according to possible working hours limitations), participants will undergo a language skills assessment to ensure the training is delivered according to their understanding and previous knowledge. Baby parking service was planned to ensure attendance continuity, though due to Covid-19 restriction measures this offer is on hold during the orientation phase (Oct. to Dec. 2020). We will reconsider the offer when starting the training hours in early 2021 and adjusting it according to the new governmental indications.

Foreseen improvements at micro-level:

- Awareness raising and improvement of interpersonal and intercultural skills
- Prevention of critical situations

- Rehabilitation and restorative interventions
- Self-help and peer support
- Actual opportunity to learn something new to enter the labour market

At meso-level, the TAIS enhances stakeholders' efforts in identifying HVG learning needs, while limiting the dispersion of resources, info and data (learners' profiling and mapping) and thus, it encourages networking and collaboration between key actors working with women victims of trafficking, fostering a shared understanding of the identified needs and rights among women victims of trafficking and support service providers.

Foreseen improvements at meso-level:

- Monitoring and improvement of work methodologies
- Material change (improvement of material conditions)
- Improved accessibility (information, opening hours, location, language)
- Procedural improvement (new or different services, methodologies)
- Changes in skills / attitude / knowledge of staff

A core process in supporting change management at macro-level is the extensive TAIS evaluation, that will provide information about what are the most and least selected training learning objectives they want to achieve and matching delivery modes selected, for institutions and local authorities to better align with real HVG needs when designing future "Learning and Training Environment" opportunities (programmes and projects).

3.2.4 Beneficiary collective/s, their needs and how these were detected, the host communities

Mutual beneficiaries are about 20 Forcibly Displaced Women (mainly Sub-Saharan) that are living and are exposed to highly vulnerable situations (e.g. Human Trafficking Victims). Benefitting as well are FDP/HVG relief, support and community centres. Long-term benefits will reach training centres and providers, teachers and trainers as well as Quintuple Helix Stakeholders.

The choice for addressing vulnerable women was a result of the context analysis, stakeholders' input and HVG fieldwork. Most female interviewees have been morally or physically neglected in childhood, raised in unhealthy or dangerous places or by people who are unable to provide them with an education. Issues such as forced marriage, abusive relationships, sexual offence attempts, forced marriages, threatening of Female Gender Mutilation (FGM) and other forms of gender-based violence are represented in women's accounts.

In Italy, there are at least 1,660 victims of human trafficking, with an ever-growing number of minors affected. Instruments to accurately collect data on trafficking in human beings (THB), therefore identify and assist victims in Italy, are still limited. This instance suggests that it is ever more urgent to implement actions aimed at integrating victims, as well as at increasing their access to and awareness of their rights, ultimately fostering acceptance and integration into and by the host community.

3.2.5 Collaborating actors

The TAIS is designed for 20 female participants. The recruitment strategy relies on the cooperation of local FDP/HVG relief, support and community centres.

The implementation is coordinated by CESIE. The internal team is composed by a local contact person, a responsible for the stakeholders' involvement; a head trainer for the supervision of the training content, methodological planning and logistics; a Trainers' Hub (4 +1 professional trainers); 4 Mentors to ensure individual and ongoing support for each of the 5 assigned mentees.

Externally the TAIS implementation is supported by the involved women support centres and by the Quintuple Helix representatives hosting a Study Visit. The cooperation is to be officially recognised with the signing of MoUs.

Advisory Board members supported the definition of learning objectives to be achieved and contribute to the participants' recruitment process.

3.2.6 *Adaptation to Covid 19*

Online implementation could theoretically be possible by recording the training sessions, though considering the vulnerable profile of beneficiaries, a new C-19 outbreak with strict social encounter limitations would definitely jeopardise the TAIS implementation success. Action-Research showed that in-presence encounters and activities are fundamental to establish a trust relationship between the parties (socio-constructive and cooperative vision of learning, where physicality and interaction are essential elements for understanding and learning).

Moreover, analysing the targets' vulnerable profiles, illiteracy may play a role when rethinking the TAIS strategy only in an online mode, as it might entail the risk of withdrawing from the path, besides generating in the participants a lack of understanding and trust, as well as a sense of frustration potentially leading to early dropouts.

3.3 Hungary

3.3.1 Basic information:

In Hungary, the objective of the TAIS is to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures. Social workers and service providers analyse individual cases in order to build a “Trajectory monitoring toolbox” of helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. It contains evidence-based “vulnerability profiles” as well as the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow in the institutional field, in order to prevent the accumulation of vulnerabilities and to reduce the isolation of vulnerable individuals.

Table 4. TAIS resume in Hungary

Menedék, Hungary		
Beneficiary collective	Social workers, service providers , vulnerable individuals	
Place	Online, June - October 2020	
Phase	Main activities of each cycle	Dates
1	Case studies from the organizations, to collect vulnerability profiles	June - Nov. 2020
2	Enhancing organizational capacities through trainings and by incorporating existing knowledge in the daily operation of the given organizations	Dec. 20 - April 2021
3	Compiling a toolbox and enhancing channels of inter-institutional cooperation and information sharing, in order to provide better services	May – Sept. 2021
	Final cross analysis	Oct. 21- Jan.2022

3.3.2 How was the design process and who participated in it?

The topic was identified based on the interviews with forcibly displaced people. These interviews showed that in Hungary, the weakness of institutions and inter-institutional coordination in the social sphere, as well as the difficult access to many institutions and services have a negative effect on the vulnerability of the forcibly displaced, therefore, this institutional network needs to be strengthened.

The Hungarian TAIS has three cycles (TAIS I, TAIS II, and TAIS III). As a first step towards the development of TAIS I, previous good practices at Menedék and other institutions have been identified. Then, two pillars were defined for the first cycle of the creative process. The first pillar was based on the concept that social workers at Menedék describe the history of complex case management of their HV clients in the form of a case study. These case studies then are considered as a primary source for the creation of vulnerability profiles. The second pillar of the concept will be the case studies from those assisting professionals (from other institutions and organizations) who have been taking an active role in vulnerable individuals’ case process by using the methodology similar to that of social workers at Menedék. The outreach activities related to this pillar will start from the second half of September, based on the ARU’s network.

The whole planning process was coordinated by Menedék's core team, as the mission of the organization makes it a central actor in the local network, furthermore it has good outreach capacity with other institutions and organizations of similar profiles. The design was validated by the ARU members, who have been continuously supportive, and by the social workers of Menedék, based on their professional experiences.

3.3.3 How did you consider and incorporate the methodology principles into the TAIS design?

3.3.3.1 RRI Responsible Research and Innovation

Interviews with FDPs were analysed by the Menedék team, from the perspective of a service provider NGO. It turned out that besides structural problems (funding for such institutions is low, the political context is hostile, and the service providing institutions are in a difficult situation), many times the root of the problem is that a client with complex vulnerabilities could not receive support at the right place, in the right time.

FDPs in Hungary often fall out of the scope of supportive services, because complex problems cannot be tackled by one service provider alone. The interview analysis with FDPs showed that coping "mechanisms" are related to a "supporting environment" of the individual, which in turn can be divided in two fields: organic and institutional. Thus, Menedék team members and ARU members agreed in the necessity to develop an institutional environment where actors engage in a non-formal, dynamic cooperation based on the organic structures of the host society, in order to improve the resilience of vulnerable individuals and groups.

Also, previous good practices were collected by Menedék and by the ARU. The projects "Let's work together for integration" or "SOS Refugees" aimed at non-formal structure building, or the "Refugee Outreach" initiative and the "Youth and Women's club" reaching out for individuals and specific groups, in order to improve their access to services they need.

A cornerstone of the TAIS methodology is the collection of existing case managements related to vulnerability profiles and experiences of social workers and service providers, the most active participants were those social workers who helped to identify cases relevant to the TAIS pilot project as well as processed the selected complex case series in a detailed, narrative case description. Furthermore, as a next step, they will identify and contact professional helpers who are able to meaningfully contribute to the text preparation. Regarding the involvement of external contributors, privacy and ethical considerations will be adopted, furthermore the support of ARU institutions will be crucial.

In the participation of TAIS the emphasis is placed on social workers, due to the fact that many times experienced social workers have a good understanding of procedures in the institutional landscape, but there is a high fluctuation in the field, and if a knowledgeable social worker leaves an organization or institution, their knowledge is lost. To address this, the central piece of the TAIS is a "toolbox" for social workers and stakeholders (including ARU member institutions) that contains evidence-based "vulnerability profiles" as well as the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow in the institutional field, in order to prevent the accumulation of vulnerabilities and to reduce the isolation of vulnerable individuals. In addition to the "vulnerability profiles" and institutional recommendations, TAIS will provide essential knowledge of how social workers can still work in the current environment for enhancing their professional development.

These “vulnerability profiles” are based on the following two sources: (1) case study descriptions of the social workers at Menedék, (2) case descriptions from assisting professionals from other organizations (including ARU member institutions) - who have been taking an active role in vulnerable individuals’ case process. The aim was that the arrangement of the texts simultaneously shows the issues of vulnerability and the supporting relationship from different perspectives.

Every circle (research, education, civil society organizations & citizens, policy makers and businesses) of the quintuple helix can benefit from profile and trajectory descriptions that contain the analysis of typical cases, a "vulnerability checklist" for clients and the intervention maps for vulnerability profiles.

Gender specific needs are not mentioned explicitly but there are strong efforts to avoid gender bias in the TAIS design and make the process open and transparent throughout. Inclusion and diversity during the design process have been considered with special attention to gender balance, ethnic diversity, and the inclusion of families – so that vulnerability can be seen from the children’s perspectives as well. The selection of targeted HV individuals were subjected to the following criteria:

- The client was defined as HV according to the RAISD research,
- The client requested assistance in multiple situations (housing solution, schooling, health care, status administration, psychological assistance, access to social aid, etc.),
- He/she as been a client of Menedék for 6 months and the social support lasted a minimum of 3 months,
- The client was living in Hungary.

Ethical concerns have been observed regarding the participants and the primary materials as well. As the texts are internal working materials therefore are read only by RAISD core staff (not even the ARU will have access to the original texts). Moreover, published materials will be anonymized, and it will not be possible to trace who were the interviewees, authors, and the clients.

3.3.3.2 Action research

The TAIS has been tailored to fit the needs of the Hungarian NGO and/or local governance context. Care practices are limited due to the harsh conditions of the local political environment and pro-refugee organizations have been taken the role to provide integration services. The aim of the Hungarian TAIS is to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures: social workers and service providers in Budapest should be informed about who, where and how would be able to apply helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. The TAIS "toolbox" for social workers and stakeholders (including ARU member institutions) will contain evidence-based "vulnerability profiles" as well as the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow in the institutional field.

Every cycle of TAIS implementation has an evaluation and feedback process that involves ARU members. Based on the trajectories in real-life situations of TAIS I, TAIS II aims at enhancing organizational capacities through trainings and by incorporating existing knowledge in the daily operation of the given organizations. Based on case analyses and stakeholder inputs, the toolbox will be finalized in the TAIS III, and channels of inter-institutional cooperation and information sharing will be built, based on the publication of a dynamic and easy-to-use guideline of trajectories to follow in the institutional landscape for different vulnerability profiles.

3.3.3.3 Socio ecological models

The TAIS will take place and affect micro and meso levels. The emphasis is on the interpersonal and individual conditions of the beneficiaries: for social workers and other helpers “reviewing” cases, reflecting on them may bring professional deepening and the possibility of supervision. More importantly, on the service provider side, it can be crucial to consider the emotional burden on social workers. A personalized approach should be helpful for preventing "vicarisation" i.e. when emotional burden takes its toll on the social worker.

In Hungary, the political context is hostile, and the service providing structures are in a difficult situation. Weakness of institutions and inter-institutional coordination in the social sphere, as well as the difficult access to many institutions and services have a negative effect on the vulnerability of the forcibly displaced. As a result, many people fall out of the scope of supportive services because complex problems cannot be tackled by one service provider alone.

Despite the abovementioned political context TAIS could be beneficial and can provide guidelines for professionals at district institutions (kindergarten, child-care facilities, family support groups) within Budapest. ARU members are supportive with these efforts.

3.3.4 Beneficiary collective/s, their needs and how these were detected, the host communities

The beneficiaries of the TAIS are the clients (vulnerable individuals) of institutions or organizations, and the social workers or service providers working with them (including ARU members).

The emphasis placed on social workers is due to the fact that many times experienced social workers have a good understanding of procedures in the institutional landscape, but there is a high fluctuation in the field, and if a knowledgeable social worker leaves an organization or institution, their knowledge is lost. It is therefore crucial to make these informal connections transferrable. ARU members can help a lot in this respect by bringing in their own expertise on different services such as psychiatric, legal or medical that are not specifically the care practices of Menedék.

Most of the interviewed VG representatives could not identify properly (by name, service period, name of the organization) specific programs designed to migrants or refugees. State-run programs are not visible due to the law changes in June 2016. Since then, the engagement on the field of integration services between state institutions (the Immigration Office or the Family Support Centers) gradually decreased and in June 2018 it was eliminated. Also, the similar or substitute services financed from the Asylum, Migration, and Integration Fund such as housing programs, language courses, labour market integration support were phased-out. Thus, there is a consensus in the ARU that there is a need for the improvement of the institutional field. The "toolbox" of vulnerability profiles as well as the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow can enhance the internal workflow of institutions and organizations, as well as the inter-institutional cooperation, in order to make trajectories less demanding, and vulnerability reduction more effective.

3.3.5 Collaborating actors

There are two participatory roles in the TAIS activities. The first, direct participants are the social workers at Menedék, as well as the assisting professionals and service providers of other institutions and organizations

(including ARU members but also representatives of other institutions). The clients (vulnerable individuals) participate indirectly through the interviews they have given for the description of their case studies.

The coordination and facilitation of the TAIS activities were strongly conducted by Menedék as the central actor. The external promoters are represented by ARU members whose contribution is significant for good communication and practices.

3.3.6 *Adaptation to Covid 19*

The Covid19 restriction and lockdown measures in Hungary have been eased in June 2020, however this might change in the coming months. In order to assure the safety of TAIS participants, some adjustments were made in the preparation.

The activities and the meetings have been developed online, and the organization have switched to remote working. So did other ARU members. These changes, however, did not have negative effects on the TAIS implementation. Furthermore, it is planned that social workers will undergo a needs/skills assessment and an online capacity building training that would help them to work with vulnerable individuals using new methods (including online communication channels).

3.4 Finland

3.4.1 Basic information:

TAIS I: To reduce the level of confinement of young men within the Finnish reception system and to promote their non-formal learning, a multilingual online forum is established. Both asylum seeking men and Finnish-speaking voluntary men are invited to join the forum. The aim is to discuss everyday life and study and work opportunities in Finland while fostering asylum seekers' language proficiencies.

TAIS2: To promote the wellbeing of asylum-seeking families with small children, day-care activities within the Finnish reception system will be developed. The current state in which the access to child-care services is restricted, the children's' integration and mental wellbeing and parents' ability to use the services they are entitled to are severely hampered. Two reception centres providing child-care services and interested in developing them further will be involved to benchmark the model of child-care services in reception centres.

Table 5. TAIS resume in Finland

Helsinki University, Finland (i)		
Beneficiary collective	Asylum seeking young men + Finnish-speaking men; Project researchers	
Place	Online	
TAIS i	Main activities of each cycle	Dates
1	Execution of the first online forum	July - August 2020
	Process evaluation of the first cycle	September - October 2020
2	Execution of the second online forum	Nov. - December 2020
	Process evaluation of the second cycle	January - February 2021
3	Execution of the third online forum	April– May 2021
	Outcome evaluation of the third cycle	June – August 2021

Helsinki University, Finland (ii)		
Beneficiary collective	Asylum seeking families + reception centre workers; Project researchers	
Place	Several reception centres	
TAIS ii	Main activities of each cycle	Dates
1	Execution of the first developmental cycle (due to lockdown measures online/phone interviews and surveys)	July - September 20
	Process evaluation of the first cycle	September - October 2020

2	Execution of the second developmental cycle	Nov. - December 2020
	Process evaluation of the second cycle	January - February 2021
3	Execution of the third developmental cycle	April -May 2021
	Outcome evaluation of the third cycle	June - August 21

3.4.2 How was the design process and who participated in it?

The design process started in June 2019 with focus group interviews of reception centre professionals (n=55). The aim of the focus groups was to discuss vulnerabilities from group and contextual perspectives – and to construct ideas on how to alleviate these vulnerabilities. The next step was to conduct interviews among asylum seekers (n=28) who were susceptible to vulnerabilities (young single men and parents with small children) in the Finnish context according to professionals. After the first two steps, more focused discussions about the possible TAIS were conducted first among the national advisory board (including Finnish Immigration Service, Finnish Red Cross, Finnish Refugee Council, former asylum seekers, Finnish Migration Institute and Association for Iraqi Women) and after that among reception centre professionals as ARU representatives and more local experts. The most active organisations in the process have been various bodies of the Finnish Red Cross. However, the whole planning process was strongly coordinated by project researchers of University of Helsinki.

3.4.3 How did you consider and incorporate the methodology principles into the TAIS design?

The main principle in the Finnish sub-project has been the involvement of key stakeholders in the process of designing the TAIS, referring particularly to asylum seekers and reception centre professionals. However, since the Finnish reception system is a highly segregated institution, legislatively and administratively isolated from other public bodies and societal sectors, the inclusion of stakeholders such as municipal authorities, several NGOs and private companies has been somewhat difficult.

3.4.3.1 RRI Responsible Research and Innovation

The need for the two TAIS that are explored in Finland arise directly from the FDP interviews. However, the potential beneficiaries or end-users rarely have ready-made solutions for their problems. This is the case particularly for asylum seekers who have limited knowledge of the surrounding institutions and their legislative foundations. This is not to say that asylum seekers would not know what is best for them, quite the contrary, but they might have difficulties in imagining what could be done within the limits of Finnish reception system. Thus, the TAIS have been and will be co-produced together with asylum seekers, researchers and other stakeholders. Moreover, in the evaluation and developmental process of the TAIS, asylum seekers will have the most focal role.

In addition to asylum seekers, several types of stakeholders have been involved in designing both TAIS. However, as explicated above, the role of public bodies and particularly private sector have been small. Some 'individual citizens' have had and will have a significant role in implementing and developing the TAIS. This mostly concerns the TAIS I while voluntary Finnish-speaking men professionally working in various sectors are involved in the design, implementation and evaluation of the TAIS.

Inclusion and diversity during the design process have been considered thoroughly. First, the two TAIS are gender sensitive. TAIS I is designed for young men while TAIS II primarily concerns mothers. Gender specific needs are recognised while at the same time gendered norms are also challenged during the TAIS implementation. Moreover, special attention has been paid to the participation of asylum seekers with different status in terms of gender, ethnicity, lingual competences and residential area. Further, we have paid attention to the diversity of our research team in terms of gender, lingual competences and national backgrounds.

The aim has been to keep TAIS design process open for constant alterations and various stakeholders operating within the reception system. Information about the project and TAIS related activities have been disseminated throughout the project trajectory particularly to Red reception centre professionals.

The main ethical principle of the research and developmental work is to go beyond the principle of 'do no harm'. This means of respecting participants' (and stakeholders') autonomy and their status as unique individuals while simultaneously recognising asylum seekers' subordinate status in the Finnish society. To do more than just avoid harming people means to come up with real life solutions to their problems in the form of co-production of TAIS. Obviously, for most asylum seekers, the problems are immediate, and the slowness of research probably feels frustrating. These types of limitations have been explained to participants in their own languages in the best possible manner. All stakeholders and interviewees have given their consent to participate in the project. As for professional stakeholders, the consent has been mostly oral while written consents have been asked from all asylum seekers.

3.4.3.2 Action research

Both TAIS I and TAIS II have been tailored to fit to the needs of two distinct sub-groups of asylum seekers: young single men and parents of small children. TAIS I is a totally new pilot and thus highly flexible to alterations throughout the process of implementation and evaluation. It is 'owned' by the RAISD project making it free of exterior regulation. TAIS II and child-care activities are more strongly embedded in the institutional structure of the Finnish reception system, even though the service is not regulated by legislation. However, reception centres have limited resources in providing child-care activities in terms of working hours, number of workers and their competences. Therefore, it might be that developmental work in TAIS II is mostly about improving the quality of the service, not its availability or intensity.

Both TAIS will be developed throughout three cycles of implementation and evaluation while asylum seekers and reception centre professionals function as key players in the game (see Deliverable 7.3). Moreover, during the previous steps, desired outcomes and evaluation criteria were discussed with both reception workers and asylum seekers. For now, both TAIS have been designed to promote the inclusion and capabilities of asylum seekers and to help them build connections outside reception centres. In addition to asylum seekers and reception centre professionals, a wider group of stakeholders will be invited to workshops between implementation cycles.

3.4.3.3 Socio ecological models

Both TAIS I and TAIS II take place and affect micro and meso levels. The main aim of the developmental work is to promote the autonomy and context-specific capabilities of individual asylum seekers. Moreover, both TAIS are interventions to professional and institutional practices in the context of Finnish reception system. As for TAIS I,

online methods, volunteering detached from place and male-specific work stances have rarely, if ever, implemented in Finnish reception centres. Further, developmental work in TAIS II aims to promote extra-statutory activities in reception centres thus redirecting the professional routines and practices. Finally, in the best-case scenario and in the long run, successful TAIS will provoke changes in the macro levels as well. In our case, the target may not be the national legislation but mostly the regulation of Finnish authorities and practices of municipalities. The legislation related to reception system is quite loose but many of the institutional practices implemented by immigration authorities and municipalities tend prevent asylum seekers agency in their surrounding communities.

3.4.4 *Beneficiary collective/s, their needs and how these were detected, the host communities*

The main beneficiaries of Finnish TAIS are asylum seekers and professionals working with them. As stated above, TAIS are designed together with key stakeholders to promote the capabilities and autonomy of two distinct sub-groups of asylum seekers. The TAIS designs are primarily based on direct knowledge acquired from asylum seekers and reception centre professionals. Moreover, the future revisions and evaluations of TAIS rely on information provided by asylum seekers and professionals.

3.4.5 *Collaborating actors*

The implementation, development and evaluation of TAIS will be coordinated by project researchers. The key participants in the process include asylum seekers, reception centre professionals and other experts together with individual volunteers. Further, national advisory board members have a key role in evaluating and developing the TAIS throughout the three cycles. The project resources without any external sponsors cover all the activities. The aim has been to develop practices that would be doable without significant material resources.

3.4.6 *Adaptation to Covid 19*

There have been few needs to adjust the TAIS activities so far due to Covid19 measures. First, despite the lockdown measures in Finland has not been very drastic, they have affected the work conducted so far. The biggest and negative affect have been the shutdowns in reception centres. As for TAIS I, we were not able to recruit asylum seeking participants in the ways and volume we wished. Due to restrictive measures, the encounters between asylum seekers and recruiting workers were very few. This led to a relatively small number of participants in the online forum. During first cycle of TAIS II we had to make more tangible changes. The original plan was to visit two reception centres and observe the child-care activities while interviewing both asylum seekers and professionals, and maybe local municipal authorities as well. Because of the restrictive measures, we were not able to visit the centres since it was forbidden and most of the child-care activities were temporarily shut down. Consequently, the whole first cycle was implemented from distance by conducting remote interviews with asylum seeking parents and e-surveying reception centre professionals.

Second, there is no guarantee that the restrictive measures would not disturb our work in the future. Right now, reception centres can provide group activities and accept visitors with some precautionary measures. However, the situation might change during this autumn.

3.5 Turkey

3.5.1 Basic information:

As behalf of accessing the rights for vulnerable groups, there is a great need to understand the various target groups within those vulnerable groups. For the TAIS implementation, in Turkish context, mainly Syrian women, but not limited to those, are the main beneficiary target group. In this TAIS, it is aimed to ensure that vulnerable groups' access and participation in basic daily life practices can be systematically followed through monitoring with participation of vulnerable groups and host community members. Because people living in Turkey, who have been forcibly displaced, they are facing some problems in gaining access to basic daily living practices. Firstly, although there are activities that ensure the realization of basic daily life practices of forcibly displaced people, these activities are sometimes insufficient. Through monitoring, it will be possible to determine in which areas additional activities are required and also necessary support is needed to be done. Secondly, forcibly displaced people cannot access and are unaware of the activities that exist due to various reasons (language barrier, cultural differences, prejudices in the host society, etc.). These examples require monitoring of those groups' rights. It also works as an advocacy work.

Table 6. TAIS resume in Turkey

Anadolou University, Turkey		
Beneficiary collective	ARUs, various stakeholder and project researchers	
Place	Co-share office and AU halls	
Phase	Main activities of each cycle	Dates
(Phase I - Step I)	1. Execution of preliminary idea and discussion meetings; Developing further TAIS steps and evaluation of steps	June - November 20
(Phase I - Step II)	2. Evaluation of decisions and suggestions	July 20 - March 21
(Phase II - Step III)	3. Diversity training cycle	Dec. 20- January 21
(Phase II - Step IV)	4. Inclusion training cycle	January - February 21
(Phase II - Step V)	5. Monitoring training	February - March 21
(Phase III - Step VI)	6. Execution of monitoring simulation	March 21-April 21
(Phase III - Step VII)	7. Execution of monitoring simulation	April 21- May 21
(Phase III - Step VIII)	8. Outcome evaluation of simulations I-II	June -November 21
(Phase IV - Step IX)	9. Final cross analysis	Oct. 21- January 22

3.5.2 *How was the design process and who participated in it?*

In terms of the design phases, the first steps took place through interviews with forcibly displaced people. The data gathered from them, secondary sources and ARU members' suggestions in addition to advisory board members created the preliminary ideas. Afterwards, separate ARU meetings took place to calibrate the ideas for TAIS segments and their implementation. Later on, we also added additional refugee group members for developing ideas. We also consulted with external academicians and specialists on the core of TAIS. In terms of ARU members' involvement, there were face-to-face meetings and online discussions because of COVID-19 period. Especially, local government, business representatives, NGOs and media representatives were almost in every meeting in addition to vulnerable group representatives. The decisions came out through the active participation of representatives, and all agreed at the end of the processes. Forcibly displaced people (vulnerable groups) participated in face-to-face meetings. Also, all project researchers and voluntary additional academicians took part in processes.

3.5.3 *How did you consider and incorporate the methodology principles into the TAIS design?*

In terms of considering and incorporating the methodology principles into the TAIS, the whole idea started mainly at the interviews with forcibly displaced people. Almost all the interviewees indicated that they were essentially lacking access to their fundamental rights and to their daily life practices in terms of health, accommodation, job opportunities, education, representation, decision making and others. Constructing on these points, the ARU members all agreed to work on these essential rights and needs based issues; accordingly, all agreed to come up with a TAIS idea for monitoring the rights. In Turkey, there is no comprehensive practices in this area (participatory monitoring). Although there are some small-scale practices but those are insufficient and they do not directly approach from the participatory monitoring perspective.

3.5.3.1 *RRI Responsible Research and Innovation*

The need for the TAIS arose fully from the beneficiary interviews of those forcibly displaced people. As being the main idea source, forcibly displaced people actively took place in the TAIS design process; that was their essential expectation also appeared in interviews. All ARU members, including research, education, civil society organizations & citizens, policy makers and businesses took part in the design of the TAIS. In terms of gender equity in the team in charge of the design of the TAIS, the ratio was 60/40 in favour female representation. All the ARU members openly and freely shared their opinions and all agreements were made with "all agreed consent". In terms of inclusion and diversity in the processes, diverse aspects of gender, age, education, social status, income, ethnicity and others were all represented by ARU members. Because of the fragility caused by COVID-19 process and sensitivity of Syrian refugee crisis, in addition to the responsibility of protecting vulnerable people, no names or other personal data were shared upon the participants' requests and also, they were able to withdraw themselves without any explanation at any moment whenever they felt so.

3.5.3.2 *Action research*

According to the proposed TAIS, the whole idea and need came from the forcibly displaced people that are interviewed. All those forcibly displaced people indicated that their voices and representations in terms of their rights were not visible in the host communities, besides all the information they have shared. Based on this point

(needs and rights), ARU members altogether analysed the situation and understood that currently, there existed no such thing as “rights monitoring” with the participation of forcibly displaced people and host community members altogether. Therefore, the new TAIS offers a truly unique and tailored approach that also stands as an example of integrative reflection of vulnerable people and host communities. All ARU members indicated that this kind of a TAIS and its design will allow them all to participate and accordingly, they will be able to reflect their true opinions and individual contributions flexibly. The design is consisted of three main cycles. The first one is preparation and consultation between stakeholders. The second cycle consists of the implementation of trainings and calibration of the work. The third cycle includes the evaluation of all the TAIS work and finalises the outcome monitoring. During the whole project period, all the stakeholders will be active contributors of the project and the TAIS in a unique way. We meet with all stakeholders on a regular base from the very beginning. We have a constant phone chain and face-to-face visits.

3.5.3.3 *Socio ecological models*

The proposed TAIS is expected to have effects in the micro and meso levels. This TAIS was designed considering the obstacles that refugees often face in their daily life in Turkey. Many of the refugees in Turkey face various challenges regarding the language, the nationality and their economic status. This situation negatively affects the integration process of refugees with the host society. The situation gets even more difficult when it comes to refugee women. When the patriarchal values of both the society those refugees come from, in this case mainly Syrian society, and the Turkish society, which is the host, combine with the difficulties of being a refugee, refugee women find themselves in a highly vulnerable and disadvantaged position among forcibly displaced groups limiting their capabilities to access their fundamental rights in accessing to daily life practices. Based on these points, the TAIS is expected to have effects on micro level activities.

It is expected that the trainings to be provided within the scope of TAIS will also have a significant impact on local government and NGO representatives, as well as persons active in business life. Bringing members of the host community and refugees together to express their views on inclusion and diversity issues will enable these institutions to reflect on what they can do about these issues. Thus, local level policy makers and business representatives can decide to carry out additional activities in the institutional level after this TAIS implementation and convey this to the competent authorities. In this respect, the TAIS is expected to have an impact in individual and institutional levels.

3.5.4 *Beneficiary collective/s, their needs and how these were detected, the host communities*

Considering the socio-cultural structure of Turkey, forcibly displaced women are likely to be in a highly vulnerable position. Therefore, refugee women are the first beneficiaries of the proposed TAIS. In the process of designing and tailoring TAIS, interviews with forcibly displaced people and ARU members, and data from the secondary sources were taken into consideration. During the interviews with FDP, we identified various problems that refugee women face in accessing fundamental rights and in accessing daily life practices. As a result, it is possible to say that the problems experienced are mainly caused by two reasons. Firstly, some of the necessities needed in daily life are not present in the refugee assistance programs in Turkey. Secondly, they do not have enough information about how to access the existing service and rights mechanisms. The latter played an influential role

in shaping and tailoring the proposed TAIS. With interviews being held regularly with forcibly displaced women, we make sure that TAIS includes the current needs of the main beneficiaries.

3.5.5 Collaborating actors

Instructors, forcibly displaced women, NGO Members, local government officials and business people will actively participate in the TAIS. Anadolu University is the coordinator of the TAIS during its implementation. There are no external promoters at the present, but AU team will negotiate for the necessary sponsorships.

3.5.6 Adaptation to Covid 19

During the implementation of the TAIS, online communication channels will be preferred if necessary, especially when communicating with trainers, ARU members and Advisory Board members outside the city. The trainings and activities are going to be carried out taking necessary health precautions following the instructions of the local health authorities. The TAIS can be partially implemented online, though not completely.

3.6 Lebanon

3.6.1 Basic information: SEED

Based on the Categorization of VGs based on D5.1 analysis in Lebanon, Health, Children, Single parents with minor children, other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence and Language Minorities were identified. The TAIS geared at addressing social, emotional, and academic problems. The program will have a positive impact on the Syrian people in camps in addition to delivering a holistic Corona Virus awareness camping to Children, pregnant women, elderly people, malnourished people, and people who are ill or immune-compromised.

LIU Health committee will work to enrich all stakeholders with the coping tools needed to enhance them in developing their awareness and minimize the challenges in facing the COVID 19 pandemic trauma.

Table 7. TAIS resume in Lebanon

LIU Lebanese International University, Lebanon		
Beneficiary collective	Project researchers, ARUs and LIU Health Committee LIU Health Committee	
Place	Online, June - October 2020	
Phase	Main activities of each cycle	Dates
1	Interviewing participants before and after the implementation; Observing improvements in displaced people's attitude and behaviour during the lockdown through the survey.	June - October 2020
2	Design and setup of Project SEAD where participants/ can choose courses they would like to attend Disseminate the following on a website: http://www.liu.edu.lb/HealthCommitee.php <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Health Awareness Messages (Video Presentation) · Social Awareness Messages (Video Presentations, audio recorded messages) · Legal Awareness Messages (Video Presentation, audio recorded messages) · Short Video Clips for Awareness Purposes (according to Training themes) 	November 2020 February 2021
3	Project researchers, ARUs and LIU Health Committee: Evaluation of met criteria and assessment of success and performance indicators.	March - May 2021
	Final Cross Analysis.	June - August 2021

3.6.2 How was the design process and who participated in it?

The design process started in May 2019 when 60 individual (outside ARU meetings) were interviewed and group presentation (within ARUs' meetings) of the project were made. That included a detailed description of the project and the framework of the project. The project was hit by the political revolution in the country from October 17 to early December 2019. This caused some delay of field interviews. By the end of December 2019 and into early January 2020, n=25 vulnerable individuals (13 Females and 12 males) who were susceptible to vulnerabilities (young single men/women and parents with small children) in the Lebanese context according to professionals were interviewed. The aim of the focus groups was to discuss vulnerabilities from group and contextual perspectives – and to construct ideas on how to alleviate these vulnerabilities.

After the interviews were completed, more focused discussions about the possible TAIS were conducted. These meetings were intended to gather information about the local context and to begin the design and test of TAISs. These organisations are: UNRWA, LASER, HOPES, British Council, International University of Beirut.

The design process was coordinated and validated by RAISD-LIU team and the ARUs. The whole planning process was strongly coordinated by RAISD-LIU team.

3.6.3 How did you consider and incorporate the methodology principles into the TAIS design?

3.6.3.1 RRI Responsible Research and Innovation

Interviews with FDPs were analysed by the RAISD-LIU team being full timers at LIU. It is worth noting that RAISD-LIU team met with VGs across Lebanon, recollected data among FDPs through interviews and identified their needs in order to implement them into the TAIS design process. LIU ARU Team applied a tool for creating a shared understanding to prioritize the top three VGs to be piloted using the Diamond 9 technique.

Based on meetings, RAISD-LIU team conducted a couple of meetings with the ARUs to discuss the challenges, and support needed. One of the challenges and problems that was addressed were the health support services that many NGOs were unable to deliver amidst the spike of Covid-19. These services had many gaps, present in the weakness of delivery mode and insufficient funds to disseminate actions that vulnerable people needed to undertake. Given the current circumstances of the pandemic of Covid-19, LIU adapted its TAIS ideas and mitigated its actions to meet the current needs of vulnerable people.

ARU recommended to disseminate a unit teamwork on health. Thus a LIUHealth committee was developed as an independent consortium. An orientation meeting by LIUHealth committee was initiated through (Google meet /Zoom meeting on **April 12, 2020**). LIU invited LIUHealth committee of 8 members with Chair presiding. The LIUHealth committee participated in a full day hands-on activities of brainstorming concepts to promote strategies on COVI-19 awareness campaign.

Parallel to the meeting, LIUhealth committee delivered **an online awareness campaign**, called **Health 4 SEAD** "Health, Social Emotional, Academic, Development". **H 4 SEAD** geared to engage in Covid-19 awareness, prevention and treatment information campaigns through on-line dissemination, but not limited to, using also community groups, telephone hotlines, flyers, posters, bulk SMS and WhatsApp messaging, radio announcements, focus group discussions, leaflets, billboards and mural drawings, broadcasted videos, as well as

brochures with instructions. The outcome of this pilot project aimed at empowering a strong pool of Syrian people in camps and Information Focal Point networks all over Lebanon in preparing them to facilitate and support them to teach Syrian, Palestinian and other origin displaced people in refugee camps through LIUI-health's active participation and sharing of practical experiences. The digital promotion topics were broadcasted through a you tube channel that include the following topics, but not limited to: <http://www.liu.edu.lb/HealthCommitee.php>

1. Developed a QA forum through <http://www.liu.edu.lb/HealthCommiteeQA.php>
2. Oriented and assisted displaced people with Post-war Stress Disorder Psychology in facing Corona and severe measures to limit the virus's infection rate by:
 - A. Supporting Children, pregnant women, elderly people, malnourished people, and people who are ill or immunocompromised.
 - B. Having correct use of medical treatment for elder people, pregnant women and children.
 - C. Improving sanitation awareness systems and health facilities.

3.6.3.2 Action research

The cycles are to develop and enhance the design of TAIS. The project will also assess all impacts associated in the design continuously. Evaluation is needed to develop and enhance the design of TAIS and will give insight on the properties of the TAIS design. The process includes collective reflexion and anticipation in terms of the outcomes. Every cycle of TAIS implementation has an evaluation and feedback process that involves RAISD-LIU and ARU members. Based on the outcomes in each cycle of TAIS, decisions are made to enhance output through trainings and by incorporating existing knowledge into operation. Based on case analyses and stakeholder inputs, results will be finalized and information sharing will be built, based on the publication of a dynamic and easy-to-use guide of outcomes to follow in the institutional landscape for different vulnerability profiles.

3.6.3.3 Socio ecological models

The Socio-Ecological Model takes into consideration the individual, and their affiliations to people, organizations, and their community at large to be effective. There are three levels (micro, meso, macro) in this model, that can be further divided in 5 stages – Individual, Interpersonal, Organizational, Community, and Public Policy.

The individual level is concerned with an individual's knowledge and skills. Knowledge about his/her health helps the vulnerable person to understand more about the issue. It helps by informing them about how susceptible they are to any health issue, how serious the health problem is, and the overall threat of the disease. Knowledge is not enough to change attitudes (most of the time but), but it helps a great deal by influencing key attitudes and decisions individuals make.

The interpersonal level has to do with a person's relationships with other people – family, friends, and so on. At this level, LIUHealth committee can reach thousands of populated areas through disseminated information online.

RAISD-LIU has the opportunity to reach more people in different sectors of the community who have features of vulnerability.

TAIS will be implemented at both micro and meso levels. The emphasis is on the interpersonal and individual conditions of the beneficiaries and assistance received by the meso level organizations.

3.6.4 *Beneficiary collective/s, their needs and how these were detected, the host communities*

The main beneficiaries of Lebanese TAIS are displaced people from Syria, Iraq and Yemen in addition to Palestinians. The Lebanese TAIS was designed together with key stakeholders from the ARU to enhance the education background of displaced people. TAIS designs are primarily based on direct knowledge acquired from interviews and the studies made in Lebanon, as well as the multiple projects implemented at LIU, which have a strong crossmatch relationship to what displaced people need. RAISD-LIU team monitors those needs with refugees, through continuous discussions regarding their experiences, knowledge, best practices and services. It is imminent that there are problems and challenges NGOs are facing. Therefore, a collective agreement on the necessity of providing efficient psychological and social support for refugees in the fields of economy, legal awareness, health, and psychological well-being is a must.

There is a unanimous agreement in the ARU that there is a need for the improvement of the displaced persons' environments. The outcomes and surveys will provide deeper understanding and set deviations if there are discrepancies in understanding what the basic needs displaced people require and what they prioritise.

3.6.5 *Collaborating actors*

The Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies" are concerned with implementing innovative services tailored to the needs of refugees in general, and vulnerable groups among FDPs in specific, as a target group for this project. The implementation, development and evaluation of TAIS will be coordinated by project researchers with help from the ARUs. Organizations and NGOs such as UNRWA, LASER, HOPES, British Council, International University of Beirut, local associations, municipalities and civil society institutions that provide services for refugees will participate in the TAIS activities. Some of these organizations are also AB members, such as UNRWA.

3.6.6 *Adaptation to Covid 19*

The Covid19 restriction and lockdown measures in Lebanon have spiked drastically between August and September in addition to the ill fate blast that hit Lebanon on August 4.

However, this might change in the coming months. In order to assure the safety of TAIS participants, some adaptations were made in advance. RAISD LIU accommodated rather than modified.

The activities and the meetings will still go on time, online, and all the work has switched to remote delivery. These changes, however, did not have negative effects on the TAIS implementation.

3.7 Jordan

3.7.1 Basic information:

Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF) aims to provide a structure significantly contribute to the well-being of individuals and prevent the need for medical support through non-clinical interventions. It will be breaking barriers creating a connection. It aims to promote awareness and understanding of the importance of Psychosocial Support System (PSS).

PRSF opens the door for the participation of stakeholders working with ARUs with members of the research team along with sharing experiences, exchanging data, and building up training programs to support the target group. Five different topics will be implemented by the PRSF through supporting: Economic Empowerment and promoting financial knowledge, social support and refugee status, health and legal awareness, and empowerment and psychological well-being. Moreover, RAISD-YU team attempts to create Refugee Support System portal "RSS", which was established to spread awareness of the benefits of PSS, provide PSS to refugees, and collect and preserve data.

Table 8. TAIS resume in Jordan

Yarmouk University, Jordan		
Beneficiary collective	Project researchers, ARUs, NGOs, refugees' workers, refugees' students, VGs among FDPs, and vulnerable people in the local community	
Place	YU halls, Online, and Several reception centres	
Phase	Main activities of each cycle	Dates
1	The team members are working with ARUs to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prepare the PSS training material and methodology Prepare the PSS evaluation methodology Elicit Requirements for RSS, identification of needs, analysis, and design. Implement first version of RSS (part of the requirement) Increase the awareness of importance of psychological support services through radio channels and social networks. 	June October 2020
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prepare Oriented Health Awareness Messages (Video Presentation) Prepare Social Awareness Messages (Video Presentations, audio recorded messages) Prepare Legal Awareness Messages (Video Presentation, audio recorded messages) Prepare Short Video Clips for Awareness Purposes (according to Training themes) 	November December 2020
2	First execution round:	January -

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hold PSS workshops Evaluate PSS material and methodology Testing and validating the RSS 	March 2021
	<p>First execution round outcome evaluations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review PSS training materials Review PSS evaluation methodology Updating PSS training materials Updating PSS evaluation methodology Modify and re-implement RSS 	April 2021
3	<p>Second execution round:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hold PSS workshops Evaluate PSS material and methodology Testing and validating the RSS 	May - August 2021
	<p>Second execution round outcome evaluations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review PSS training materials Review PSS evaluation methodology Updating PSS training materials Updating PSS evaluation methodology Modify and re-implement RSS 	September – October 2021
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Release the PRSF result Cross analysis 	November 2021

3.7.2 How was the design process and who participated in it?

The design process started in August 2019, with refugee interviews. 30 interviews had been held. During that interviews, RAISD-YU team asked many questions and saved notes. RAISD-YU team spent two months reading previous reports and literature to have ideas about best and bad practices in dealing with refugees in Jordan.

Early in 2020 several workshops had been held with diverse ARU members from different organizations (Local, global, and public), and session with refugees. During these sessions, RAISD-YU team explained the meaning of TAIS, the aim, the concept of RRI, the evaluation, what was expected, and their notes on the held interviews and focus group meetings with refugees and what they got from previous studies and reports. RAISD-YU team discussed the challenges, needs and services refugees face in the host country with ARUs and the selected group of refugees. Then, RAISD-YU team and ARUs discussed different strategies and as a result, Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF) had been selected.

The design process was coordinated and validated by RAISD-YU team and ARUs. The whole planning process was strongly coordinated by RAISD-YU team.

3.7.3 How did you consider and incorporate the methodology principles into the TAIS design?

3.7.1.1 RRI Responsible Research and Innovation

The FDP had an active role in the TAIS design process, based on analysing the experiences FDPs have gone through in the host country. It is worth noting that RAISD-YU team have met with VGs among FDPs through interviews and focus groups meetings and have identified their needs in order to implement them in TAIS design process.

When it came to the stakeholders' participation of the TAIS design, (25) participants from more than 25 NGOs and local organizations, which are working in Jordan to support refugees in different areas such as Law, Health, Education, Civil Society, and Social Inclusion, were included.

RAISD-YU team conducted several meetings with the ARUs to discuss the challenges, needs and type of services refugees face in the host country. One of the challenges and problems that was addressed is the psychological support services that many NGOs had conducted and implemented previously. These services had many gaps represented in the weakness of the training materials, recruitment of some unqualified PSS trainers, inappropriate psychological support services in terms of refugees need, and insufficient fund that only cover a small group of people although there is a great number of refugees in desperate need for PSS. Therefore, RAISD-YU team and the ARUs highlighted these gaps and agreed that the TAIS needs perfectly arose from the aforementioned challenges. Also, the TAIS needs heavily relied on finding qualified experts in the PSS, building up well-developed training materials related to psychological support, and working on effective assessment and evaluation of the training materials.

For sustainability purposes, it was suggested that it is important to create an online platform that would provide psychological support services to refugees online. There was a collective agreement on the TAIS needs and on the TAIS design process. The participants have agreed on topics related to PSS and decided, along with the help and experience of RAISD-YU team, to design a set of training modules to be delivered in the near future.

We noticed that all stakeholders were enthusiastic to help design and attend such training as they recognize the benefits from sharing and analysing refugees' data, especially the vulnerable groups. Consent forms were signed by TAIS participants. The terms and conditions included (not) sharing photos and images of participants during the workshops, reserving copy rights of the training material, and personal data exchange.

The ARUs began to prepare the training material under the supervision of RAISD-YU team and Dr. Ahmad Alshraifin—a specialist and a professor of psychological counselling and mental health. The ARUs were trained on how to create an effective training program which connects between theory, practice, and social values. Also, Dr. Nader Rifai (a specialist in assessment and evaluation) trained the ARUs on Evaluation process and methods.

Gender equity was incorporated in the design of TAIS. In Jordan, the majority of NGOs and local organizations employees are highly educated women. Therefore, the number of female participants taking part in the ARUs is bigger than male participants.

3.7.1.2 Action research

After conducting multiple workshops with ARU members to design the TAIS, participants designed strategies to provide social and psychological support for highly vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced people. The design is tailored as follows:

- Legal and social group
- Economic empowerment and psychological pressure of highly vulnerable refugees.
- International/Humanitarian legal support
- Psycho-social empowerment of highly vulnerable refugees

The TAIS design and process is systematically flexible and collaborative. ARUs and RAISD-YU team deliver the benefits of innovation in design. The focus is on two aspects of the design process: project co-design, and collaboration mechanism. It was found that both aspects enable innovation by driving project actors (ARUs and RAISD-YU team) to learn about the design space and develop a shared understanding of the design problem. Learning through shared understanding not only improves the objective value but also enhances the design's outcomes.

The cycles are meant to develop and enhance the design of TAIS. Also, the evaluation will assess all impacts associated to the design. The partial evaluation is needed to develop and enhance the design of TAIS and will give insight on the properties of the TAIS design. The process includes collective reflexion and anticipation in terms of the outcomes:

1. The participants will finish designing their strategies to provide social and psychological support for highly vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced people.
2. The ARUs will provide valuable ideas and suggestion to improve (RSS).
3. Those ARUS that are trained in methodologies for designing and implementing strategies are expected to share their experience and training programs with YU RAISD team.

The ARUS were divided into four groups based on the theme of the strategy that will be built and, later, implemented. Each group was asked to create a Whatsapp group and conduct meetings to design strategies. Each group referred to RAISD-YU team and discussed the adjustments and adaptations of the design. RAISD- YU team began to build (RSS) a web application which will be open to all stakeholders throughout the project. They are invited to participate in adding value, ideas, experiences, and data to improve (RSS).

TAIS documents outline the training objectives and competencies that will be acquired following the PRSF, as well as the didactic and evaluation orientations of a methodology that would best promote competencies. These recommendations can be materialized into the following:

- Promote both group and individual work between ARU members.
- Develop both theoretical and practical content.

- Record theoretical sessions for their 'open-access' availability.
- Simulation of practical situations presented either in real life or in videos using situational variables.
- Use of active RRI methodologies such as Case Studies, or learning based on FDP problems.

A Research will be drafted in which the theoretical and practical content will be developed. The theory for each of the topics included in the PRSF's guidelines will be grouped into different dimensions such as VGs and political rule development; impairments associated with VGs of FDPs in situations of social vulnerability; evaluation model and diagnosis in refugee and psychological intervention. Furthermore, this research will include a proposal for the training of future trainers.

TAIS will be developed throughout three cycles, the first cycle including TAIS preparing through two time slots. The second and third cycle have also two time slots for the implementation and evaluation as presented in Table 1. In the second and third cycle, desired outcomes and evaluation criteria will be discussed with both RAISD-YU team and a wider group of stakeholders including ARUs.

3.7.1.3 Socio ecological models

We will use the socio-environmental model "framework for prevention". Aim to turn off psychiatric interventions. Prevention requires an understanding of the factors that affect the psychological dimensions of VGs in FDPs, and these factors include the individual and institutional properties. So, we will use a two-level socio-environmental model; Micro and Meso. These levels will give better understanding of the psychological problems and the impact of potential prevention strategies. These models consider the complex interaction between individual, relationship, community, and societal factors. This mechanism allowed us to understand the group of factors that the VGs in Jordan were exposed to, to psychological danger, or to protect them from the exposure to psychological problems.

3.7.4 Beneficiary collective/s, their needs and how these were detected, the host communities

"Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies" are concerned with implementing innovative services tailored to the needs of refugees in general and vulnerable groups among FDPs in specific as a target group for this project. It is worth noting that these needs were enumerated after RAISD-YU team had met with VGs among FDPs through focus groups meetings and have identified their needs in order to implement them in TAIS design process. In addition, RAISD-YU team have met with the ARUs and shared a few discussions regarding their experiences, knowledge, best practices and services with refugees. It was noted that there were problems and challenges that faced NGOs when they were providing PSS to refugees. Therefore, there was a collective agreement on the necessity of providing efficient psychological and social support for refugees in the fields of economy, legal awareness, health, and psychological well-being.

After conducting multiple workshops with ARU members and focus group meetings with refugees to design the TAIS, participants designed strategies to provide social and psychological support for highly vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced people. The TAIS have positive implications on the well-being and agency of refugees benefiting from the PSS which will affect positively on the host community. Also, PSS services provided through the training programs and RSS will decrease negative and harmful coping strategies, enhance the resilience of individuals, families, and communities, and reduce the need for medical counselling.

Our beneficiaries will be varied. For example, youth; young women and men will be our beneficiaries for Economic Empowerment and Promoting Financial Knowledge, while any age group can involve with any PRSF sessions:

- Introduction to PSS and Social Support and Refugee Status
- PSS and Social Support through Health Awareness
- PSS and Social Support through Empowerment and Psychological Well-being
- PSS and Social Support through Legal Awareness

3.7.5 Collaborating actors

The implementation, development and evaluation of TAIS will be coordinated by project researchers with a help from the ARUs. NGOs, local associations, municipalities and civil society institutions that provide PSS services for refugees will participate in the TAIS activities. RAISD-YU team are the coordinators and facilitators. RAISD-YU team is trying to get promoters and sponsors to take part in the TAIS.

3.7.6 Adaptation to Covid 19

The TAIS were adapted to the current Covid-19 breaks. The ARUs were divided into five teams to design the training material. Each team was asked to create a WhatsApp group to maintain the development and the design of their training material in order to reduce physical meetings. With the current increase of coronavirus cases in Jordan, we anticipate a delay of the implementation of the training programs. The TAIS cannot be carried out 100% online. Another anticipated risk is that participants might be discouraged to take part in the TAIS due to Covid-19 precautions. Also, the number of refugees receiving the PSS might decrease.

Conclusion

The past half year has been a challenging time for research and innovation activities globally and even more demanding for projects dealing with Forcibly Displaced People and Vulnerable Groups. Covid-19 crisis brought disease and a health system crisis, but also a social and economic storm of unforeseen extensions, that has further widened the gap between well off, well doing people and vulnerable people, between rich and poor neighbourhoods, between forced migrants and local population. Working with forced migrants during the pandemic has been arduous: locating potential beneficiaries becomes more difficult as they were dealing with more pressing needs, activities that are usually face-to-face have to move online to provide them continuity, generating new problems, for instance, to provide beneficiaries online access to the activities included in the different TAIS strategies and action lines in the seven participating countries. These adaptation tasks faced to a situation where collaborating stakeholders were overwhelmed by the emergency and have to prepare their own social intervention online, which requires strong efforts of adaptation. So, the coronavirus situation has added “one more stitch” to the tailoring of the attention and inclusion strategies that compose our TAIS that we have addressed properly.

The efforts of the past months resumed in this report showed that our consortium has gained in confidence and all the partners fluently apply the methodological principles (RRI; action research, socio-ecological models) and almost all the rules and recommendations they imply, to the point that we can say that these have become embedded in the TAIS design and implementation process. Issues related to collaborative work methods, democratic governance, inclusion and diversity, deep ethics and specific protection measures of forcibly displaced people have been considered. Related to gender, we have achieved gender balance, so we will work from now on to improve the application of a global perspective regarding these aspects. Also, transparency plays an important role in the project: all the activities of the project generate reports that are available for the examination and feedback of all collaborators and external public. Only information that could affect the security or privacy of participants is not disclosed following the ethics guidelines of the project.

RAISD consortium members started the TAIS design process in the first quarter of 2020 and by July 2020, all the countries had a clear implementation plan, and some of the partners had even started with the first steps of their application. The main TAIS activities are planned to take place in Phase 1 (in autumn 2020), and Phases 2 and 3 (from December 2020 to September 2021), with a partial evaluation between phases that considers all the available information until that moment. Phase 4 is entirely dedicated to the cross-country evaluation of the TAIS final results in the 7 project countries. Along this process, the consortium will continuously monitor what adjustments and adaptations will be required to adapt the TAIS to the changing conditions of today's liquid world, and especially to modifications in local migration policies and living conditions of forcibly displaced people. The key feature for adapting our TAIS to the forthcoming conditions is having resilience, anticipating difficulties, and, above all, listening to our beneficiaries and other stakeholders. In this sense, we have to improve four aspects that we are going to address in the last stage:

- 1) Implement strategies to ensure all partners are confident in applying the methodological approach in all phases.
- 2) Improve the inclusion of VG among FDP in all spheres of the project.
- 3) Ensure a higher involvement of all the stakeholders, mainly host communities.
- 4) Distil recommendations that can affect macro level policies.

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Del. 3.3 TAIS methodology and guidelines. Preliminary version [September, 2020]

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